

THE STUDY OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS IN FOOTBALL TEAMS

Majidov Jasur Bakhtiyarovich

Associate Professor, Department of Psychology, Jizzakh State Pedagogical
University

E-mail: majidov-jdpi@mail.ru

Abstract: This article examines the psychological aspects of interpersonal relationships in professional football teams within the framework of sports psychology. Particular attention is given to the specific features of interaction within the team as a small social group, including cohesion, psychological climate, group communication, and coach–athlete relationships. The analysis of existing studies indicates that interpersonal relationships in professional football teams remain an underexplored issue despite their significant impact on team performance and effectiveness.

Keywords: football, sports group, cohesion, professional football team, interpersonal relationships, coach, athlete.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы изучения межличностных отношений в профессиональных футбольных командах в рамках спортивной психологии. Особое внимание уделяется специфике взаимодействия в команде как в малой социальной группе, включая такие аспекты, как сплочённость, психологический климат, групповая коммуникация и взаимоотношения между тренером и спортсменами. Анализ существующих исследований показывает, что проблема межличностных отношений в профессиональных футбольных командах остаётся недостаточно изученной, несмотря на её значимость для повышения эффективности спортивной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: футбол, спортивная группа, сплочённость, профессиональная футбольная команда, межличностные отношения, тренер, спортсмен.

In the field of sports psychology, research into interpersonal relationships within sports teams has been gaining significant momentum. Recent studies have highlighted the importance of sports teams as small groups, focusing on areas such as team cohesion, psychological climate, group interaction, social perception, group communication, athlete readiness, and, most notably, the coach-athlete relationship.

However, interpersonal dynamics within professional football teams remain one of the less explored subjects. Despite this, many studies are gaining recognition for their focus on the personality of the athlete. Early efforts to examine the unique personality traits of football players can be traced back to the Brazil national team. It is noted that following their 1958 World Cup victory in Sweden, all players underwent psychological testing. Yet, these studies failed to attract widespread attention because they primarily focused on assessing the players' abilities and intelligence—information that coaches already possessed. Consequently, such research delayed the integration of professional psychological services into football.

Nevertheless, the necessity of studying football teams as a reference group remains highly relevant. Subsequent research has demonstrated that psychologists in the team-oriented sport of football must address and investigate the following key areas:

1. Studying the personal and individual characteristics of each football player;
2. Examining interpersonal relationships within the team;
3. Analyzing the socio-psychological climate within the group;
4. Providing direct psychological support to both athletes and coaches [10].

A sports group is a specific type of small group. Such a group typically consists of at least two and no more than 25 individuals, unified by common sports

activity goals under the supervision of a coach, instructor, or referee. E. V. Melnik and J. K. Shemet identify the number of members as a defining characteristic of a sports team. According to their view, a sports group constitutes a collective of 2 to 25 people (for instance, a football team consisting of 11 players) [8].

Numerous studies have attempted to demonstrate the impact of the psychological climate within a team on its performance efficiency. Accordingly, it is believed that a positive emotional climate is directly linked to team cohesion on one hand, and operational effectiveness on the other. Examples of this are widespread in sports practice; a decline in a particular team's performance is often attributed to a decrease in solidarity among its players.

British psychologists David Ponsonby and Maurice Yaffé discovered that in high-pressure situations, football players are more likely to pass the ball to teammates whom they hold in high regard. Video analysis revealed that this occurs automatically and subconsciously, even in cases where players had received strict instructions from coaches to avoid such bias. Generally, it is important to note the inconsistency of findings in social psychology regarding this issue. In some instances, a high level of cohesion had a positive impact on performance results, while in others, excessive solidarity actually hindered effective activity. According to David Ponsonby, teams whose members felt less of a need for friendly ties were often more successful than those composed of players requiring warm and close interpersonal relationships.

In the coach-athlete relationship, a high level of mutual understanding is considered a primary factor in the emergence of satisfaction with one's performance. In the studies of S. Jowett, the moral and emotional factors of collaborative activity, the specific nature of social perceptiveness, and the ethical obligations of both coaches and athletes were examined [1].

Orosz, R. (2015) and colleagues conducted extensive research on the psychological factors involved in developing talent among young football players.

The study involved 425 players from Hungarian youth and junior championships, along with 21 of their coaches. The primary objective of the research was to demonstrate the role of psychological factors in talent development within football. By analyzing the athletes' levels of self-awareness, psychological immunity, team perception, and the coach-athlete relationship, the researchers substantiated several key psychological drivers for talent growth. Specifically, they emphasized that the integration of traits such as low anxiety, self-confidence, the ability to maintain self-control in difficult situations, and—most importantly—positive cooperation in relationships with coaches and teammates serves as a crucial indicator for talent development and achieving overall efficiency [9].

In recent decades, research has intensified regarding the role of sports psychologists in organizing psychological services and fostering effective interpersonal relationships within sports teams. This growing body of research has led to the publication of numerous scientific articles and monographs. Notably, British scholar M. Nesti, drawing on a decade of professional experience at the elite level of English football, offers a comprehensive guide on delivering psychological services within a team environment—ranging from practical on-field training to shaping organizational behavior at the club level. The book addresses all critical issues that define the role of a modern professional sports psychologist in football, including:

- Developing cognitive and mental skills in athletes;
- Group cohesion and team dynamics;
- The structure of management and coaching activities, interpersonal relationships within the team, and other related topics.

The significance of this work lies in its rich combination of theory and practice, presenting a holistic approach to psychology in football based on research conducted across sixteen professional clubs in five European countries. Consequently, it serves as an essential manual for all psychologists and coaches working in professional team sports.

In conclusion, the study of interpersonal relationships in football teams continues to evolve, driven by the practical experiences and psychological services provided by sports psychologists within the collective.

References:

1. Jowett, S., Adie, J.W., Bartholomew, K.J., Yang, S.X., Gustafsson, H., Lopez-Jiménez, A.: Motivational processes in the coach-athlete relationship: a multi-cultural self-determination approach. *Psychol. Sport Exerc.* 32, 143–152 (2017)
2. Коломейцев Ю.А. Взаимоотношения в спортивной команде. М.: Физкультура и спорт, 1984. 128 с
3. Nesti M. *Psychology in Football, Working with Elite and Professional Players*. London-2010.;p-216.
4. Majidov, J. (2021). СПОРТДАГИ МУЛОҚОТ ИЖТИМОЙ ПСИХОЛОГИК ҲОДИСА СИФАТИДА. *Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании*, 1(1).
5. Majidov, J. B. (2020). Some characteristics of relationships in football teams. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 1981–1988.
6. Majidov Jasur. (2023). PROFESSIONAL FUTBOL JAMOASIDA FUTBOLCHILAR TOMONIDAN JAMOANI IDROK ETISHNING O‘ZIGA XOSLIGI . *International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research*, 273–277.
7. Огородова Т. В. Психология спорта. Учебное пособие. Ярославль, 2013,-с 120.
8. Orosz, R., & Mezo, F. (2015). Psychological factors in the development of football-talent from the perspective of an integrative sport-talent model. *Journal for the Education of Gifted Young Scientists*, 3(1), 58-76.

9. Хигир.Б. Ю. Психологический анализ в большом футболе. Москва 2017 г, 184 с.

10. Nodira, F. (2018). Specificity of interaction between teacher and students in the process of teaching a foreign language. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (8 (20)), 141-143.